

A Seminar Report

On

Web Form User Interface Evaluation

Submitted To:-

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Course-

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Submitted by:-

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1. Introduction

In this Interactive System, We tried to make a evaluation system based upon Web forms and covering the evaluations on functional factors as World Wide Web consist of number of different types of pages which requires some comparisons between which web page with a form is more better for the User Experience as compare to some other form having same design but some new functionality.

Providing information into the web forms can be a different approach for different number of users. Some user's prefer to check form data number of times in order to provide Accuracy before its submission while some user want to spend less number of time with some guarantee that provided user data fulfills the criteria set by the specific Web based form. This same type of approach we tried and look over a similar design having a real time validation check on its input field while other one having validations with same number of criteria, validation check on all available fields being done only at the end of submission.

With the consideration of some evaluation parameters, we will try to differentiate between functional factor of validation in real time on input fields and validation check on all of the fields after submission of whole form.

2. Related Work

There are number of guidelines/ methods being available to have an evaluation of efficient web form based upon validations being done on web forms either displaying the error message while filling the input field or after filling out whole form validation result in nature or error message will arrive.

For our Evaluation method, we have taken into consideration of [J.A. Bargas-Avila et al. / Interacting with Computers 19 \(2007\) 330–341](#) which aims to compare web forms which displays error messages in different formats like:-

1. Afterward, embedded all at once: with help of server side validation, after form filling error messages will be returned back all.
2. Afterward, dialogue , all at once: validation will be provided in form of dialogue boxes will all error based results.
3. Afterward, dialogue, one by one: after every submission of the form , one by one , errors will be provided in dialogues boxes.
4. Immediate Dialogue: After completing of every input field user will be provided with result of validation at same time with error message.

For our paper, we have selected 1. and 4. approach to make the work simple and more oriented towards error messages on submission of form and real-time (immediate) error message response after input field data entry with respect to validation criteria of form.

The related work[1.] also used some efficient measurement techniques of objectives measures like:

2.1 Timing: Time required to completely fill a from start till end, faster completion rates results in more efficient form

2.2 Error rate: Amount of errors occurs during form completion

2.3 Subjective rating: based upon user satisfaction

For the measurements , we taken into consideration methods and some different approach like:

- **Timing:** We are evaluating whole form and in between fields as well.
- **Number of clicks:** which tells fixed number of clicks required to complete a form(related with error rare)
- **Error rate:** dependent upon number of required clicks.
- **Subjective and Covariate measure** based upon user ease of use and participant information being collected.

The Related work[1.] paper dealing more with when and how should the error message being displayed whereas we will focus towards: When it is suitable to display error message.

3. Design

Here we will provide information about our basic design and advanced design:

Full Name: sa

dd/mm/yyyy

Email Address: jhvjh@gmugy.

Telephone Number: 331233123313123

Programming Language: Svelte

Operating Systems: macOS Linux Windows

Gender: Male Female

Age: 23

UX:Preference(0-6): 4

- time for task: 549.621s
- the mouse position is 8 x 45
- click count: 0
- time per task:0

Confound factors:

- Gender:Male
- Age:23
- UX:Preference:4

Fig. 2.1 Basic Design(at once all validations)

Full Name: sa

31/12/1996

Email Address: jhvjh@gmugy.

57567576575755765

Programming Language: Svelte

Operating Systems: macOS Linux Windows

Gender: Male Female

Age: 23

UX:Preference(0-6): 4

- time for task: 267.276s
- the mouse position is 23 x 300
- click count: 0
- time per task:0

Confound factors:

- Gender:Male
- Age:23
- UX:Preference:4

user.fullName must be at least 3 characters

user.email must be a valid email

user.phone must be at most 15 characters

Fig. 2.2 Advance Design(one by one Validations)

The Functional factors are F1 and F2 can be represented with design as:

1. F1 having level 0 and level 1 in which **level 0** is the basic design and **level 1** is the new approach design(Advance), these are ordinal values.

Both design are web forms having Input Fields and Buttons, Check boxes and some radio buttons and right-side div having measurements being received from these input in form of clicks and time-stamps.

2. F2 having level 0 and level 1 in which **level 0** depicts validations are being only displayed in form of error messages just below the input fields after the submission of form with “Submit” button click.

Level 1 also does validation with display of error messages but with immediate response as soon as user completes the input field, error message will be displayed just below the input field, if user is not following the criteria of validation of respective input field.

4. Methodology

In methodology, we will introduce our Independent/dependent variables along with Factors considered, Concrete hypothesis and Measures taken.

Independent variables: Validations on Form either at **All at once on form submission** or **Immediate Response(One by One)**

Dependent variables: Measurement of **Time, Accuracy** of form completion

In this UI, We have used **Functional factor:** Validation

Level 0: Validation on Form Submission (Vs)

Level 1: Validation Immediately after Completion of data entry on Input Fields (Vf)

Concrete Hypothesis: There are two kinds of Hypothesis being considered, (i) Error hypothesis (ii) Time hypothesis

Error-Hypothesis: When we used validate property on both forms design, we found that (Vf) variant 2 Immediate Validation was taking less errors(less number of repetition required in Input fields data correction) as compare to (Vs) variant1 validation on submit.

Time-Hypothesis: (Vf) variant 2 Immediate validation took less amount of form completion time significantly as compared to (Vs) variant 1 Validation on submit, as from (i)hypothesis, we can say that if number of errors are considering to be low and less number of interaction required(clicks and data entries) then time will be also automatically less.

Measures taken into account for hypothesis:

1.Error rates: By collecting the number of errors(more then required number of clicks) can help us to tell about the which approach have less number of errors by participants and from that we will know which approach is more suitable method .

2.Time to complete: By collection time stamps of time required to complete a form from starting till submission of form(in between input fields time as well), as faster completion time depicts efficiency as well as less time (interaction) needed by participants to complete the form successfully.

5. Report on Data

Descriptives

	Versions	tf(Speed)	error rate	ccc
N	v1	50	50	50
	v2	50	50	50
Mean	v1	19092	0.0920	7.58
	v2	19790	0.0580	7.38
Median	v1	18401	0.00	7.00
	v2	19752	0.00	7.00
Standard deviation	v1	4604	0.175	1.34
	v2	4951	0.0928	0.725
Minimum	v1	11316	0.00	6
	v2	11690	0.00	6
Maximum	v1	33069	1.00	14
	v2	36381	0.300	9

Table 5.1

All evaluations are performed in milliseconds(ms)

Based upon the given data in terms of Total Time to complete the form(tf), number of error occurrence(error rate), number of clicks(ccc), we get to know firstly the sample size is same for both variants(50,50), In terms of Time: The time taken

for both variant is significantly near to each other while the error rate of Variant V2 is less as compared to Variant V1, based upon the number of clicks which remained 7, in order to complete all fields correctly, can be seen almost same for both the variants.

Descriptives

	Versions	tuf	tef	tpf
Mean	v1	5257	13027	18106
	v2	5610	13128	18407
Median	v1	4535	12838	17553
	v2	4898	12151	18058
Standard deviation	v1	2915	4405	4730
	v2	2866	4837	5053

Table 5.2

From above given data, Time taken for form completion can be more justified as in between of form, three fields time, username(tuf), tef(email), tpf(phone) completion times are being noted. From the given information, It is again depicting the timing of completion of these three fields is again almost same except slight variation in username field as v2 as compared to v1 as in Fig 5.1.

Independent Samples T-Test

Independent Samples T-Test

	Statistic	df	p	
tf(Speed)	Student's t	-0.730	98.0	0.467
error rate	Student's t	1.215	98.0	0.227

Assumptions

Normality Test (Shapiro-Wilk)

	W	p
tf(Speed)	0.959	0.003
error rate	0.624	<.001

Note. A low p-value suggests a violation of the assumption of normality

Group Descriptives

	Group	N	Mean	Median	SD	SE
tf(Speed)	v1	50	19091.8200	18401	4604.068	651.1135
	v2	50	19790.2200	19752	4950.9629	700.1719
error rate	v1	50	0.0920	0	0.175	0.0247
	v2	50	0.0580	0	0.0928	0.0131

Table 5.3

The independent sample test was performed as both Variants, are independent to each other and there was no significant difference between timing of both variant found in this case.

In case of error rate, the mean different found to be significant and variant 2 is showing less amount of errors as compared to variant 1.

One-Way ANOVA

	F	df1	df2	p
tf(Speed)	0.534	1	98	0.467
error rate	1.476	1	98	0.227

	Versions	N	Mean	SD	SE
tf(Speed)	v1	50	19091.8200	4604.0680	651.1135
	v2	50	19790.2200	4950.9629	700.1719
error rate	v1	50	0.0920	0.1748	0.0247
	v2	50	0.0580	0.0928	0.0131

Table 5.4

One-Way Anova is chosen here, as we have only single independent variable from both of the factors.

An one-way Anova confirmed that there were no significant differences for speed(time) with $F(1,98)=0.534, p=0.467$

While for error rates the difference seems to be significant as evaluation are performed in milliseconds, with $F(1,98)=1.476, p=0.227$

Subjective Ratings(Confound Measures):

	Versions	Gender	Q(Preference)	Age
Mean	v1	Male	3.73	25.5
		Female	3.40	24.5
	v2	Male	4.30	25.5
		Female	3.90	24.5
Median	v1	Male	4.00	25.0
		Female	4.00	24.5
	v2	Male	4.50	25.0
		Female	4.50	24.5
Standard deviation	v1	Male	1.50	3.20
		Female	1.51	1.58
	v2	Male	0.992	3.20
		Female	1.73	1.58

Table 5.5

(Likert scale is from 0-6 is used for Preference)

In Confound measures, The number of participants

were 10, where 8 Men and 2 Women participated. The maximum age of participants is between 21 upto 31, where the mean age of participant is found to be between 24-25 and preference choice for Variant V2 is found to be more in both Men and Women.

For final results , based upon data retrieved from evaluations we can conclude that our hypothesis for Time: is not correct as time is found to be significantly same for both variants.

For Error Hypothesis: based upon evaluated data the hypothesis is justified as (Vf) variant 2 comes with less number of errors as compared to (Vs) variant 1.

6. Discussion

The test depicts that the both variants resulted in nearly same amount of time for users till the form, but the number of errors coming into variant 2 was less as compared to variant 1, so we can say that it is better to use form with real time validations.

From our UI's variants, we can say more amount of measurements would be more helpful like from **table 5.1**, the number of number of clicks required on fields was coming very near for both variants, which we believe can change if according to **table 5.5**, more participants(suppose 100), with age group of 12-80 and of different genders takes part can result in different amount time taken as well change in amount of clicks required.

The paper[1.] plays a key role to identify how mixture of different forms with different behaviors can result in different time and error rate and likewise approach was tried in our real time and on submit validation forms.

We can say, If we would have endless budget and time, we can afford very close results which is choice of user and based upon such in-depth evaluations can identify future UI's demand.

7. References

[1.] Javier A. Bargas-Avila, Glenn Oberholzer, Peter Schmutz, Marco de Vito, Klaus Opwis, Usable error message presentation in the World Wide Web: Do not show errors right away, *Interacting with Computers*, Volume 19, Issue 3, May 2007, Pages 330–341.

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[2.] Usability Metric

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<https://users.sussex.ac.uk/~grahamh/RM1web/F-ratio%20table%202005.pdf>

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Apart from these reference link's lectures(Interactive Systems) plays a key roles to get some new ideas about design and measurements.